

EXPLORING THE EFFECT OF PRE-READING VOCABULARY ACTIVITIES ON A2- B1 LEVEL STUDENTS' ABILITY TO UNDERSTEND MAIN IDEAS IN SHORT TEXTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18206145>

Abstract

This exploratory action research investigates the impact of a newly introduced pre-reading vocabulary activity on A2-B1 level students' ability to understand the main idea of short texts. The study involved 14 students divided into control and experimental groups. The control group completed reading texts using traditional methods, while the experimental group engaged in a visual and context-based vocabulary prediction strategy prior to reading. Data collected from comprehension tasks showed that the experimental group outperformed the control group, scoring an average 11-12 correct answers out of 13, compared to the control group's 7-8. The findings suggest that pre-reading vocabulary activities incorporating contextual guessing and visual support significantly enhance students' comprehension of main idea.

Keywords: Pre-reading activities, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, main idea, contextual guessing, visual support, exploratory action research.

Introduction

Reading comprehension is an essential component of language learning, and understanding the main idea of a text is considered a core skill for B1-level learners. However, many students at this proficiency level struggle to identify the main idea due to insufficient vocabulary knowledge. Prior studies have indicated that pre-reading activities, especially vocabulary-focused ones can help reduce lexical barriers and increase overall comprehension by preparing student for the reading content. In many classrooms, reading continues to be taught through traditional read-and-answer routines, which often overlook the importance of preparatory vocabulary work. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the effect of a new pre-reading vocabulary activity on A2-B1 level students' comprehension of short texts. The method combines contextual guessing with visual inferencing, providing learners with opportunities to engage more actively with unfamiliar vocabulary before reading. This research seeks to answer the following question:

To what extent does a visual and contextual pre-reading vocabulary activity improve B1-level students' ability to understand the main ideas of short texts?

Method.

This study employed an exploratory action research design to investigate the effectiveness of a newly introduced pre-reading vocabulary activity A2-B1 level students' ability to comprehend the main idea of short texts. The action research approach was selected because it allows the teacher-researcher to implement pedagogical innovations, observe their impact in real classroom conditions, and make data-driven decisions for improvement. The research was conducted at a local educational institution with a total of 14 A2-B1 level students, aged between 13-14. the students were randomly divided into two equal groups: Control group (n=7) and experimental group (n=7) All students shared similar proficiency levels and had previously studied reading strategies as part of their curriculum. Two reading texts were selected and adapted to A2-B1 proficiency standards. Each text contained short paragraphs, target vocabulary items and comprehension tasks. Assessment instruments included: Gap-filling exercises, True/False/Not given questions, Vocabulary recognition tasks. Main idea comprehension questions. The experimental group additional received visual vocabulary cards, each containing an illustrative image and a corresponding word written on the back. The study was conducted over two lessons and included the following procedures: Read the passage individually, Completed gap-filling exercises, Answered true/false/not given questions. Most students scored 7-8 out of 13, indicating moderate comprehension. Experimental group (new pre-reading vocabulary activity) The experimental group engaged in a new vocabulary-focused pre-reading method consisting of three stages; Students read the text and underlined unfamiliar vocabulary items without any explanation from the teacher. Students received picture cards with target vocabulary printed on the back. Without checking the written words, students used the pictures and textual context to infer the meaning of the unfamiliar words. After completing the vocabulary inference activity, students answered the same comprehension questions as the control group. Almost all students achieved 11-12 out of 13 correct answers, demonstrating noticeable higher comprehension and more accurate main idea identification. Data were collected from students' task results and classroom observations. Descriptive statistics were used to compare the performance of the control and experimental groups. The number of correct responses was analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the new pre-reading vocabulary method.

Results

The results indicate that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group. Students who engaged in contextual and visual vocabulary prediction demonstrated stronger reading comprehension and were better able to identify the main idea of the texts. Control group average: 7-8 correct answers out of 13. Experimental group average: 11-12 correct answers out of 13. The difference in performance suggests that unfamiliar vocabulary was the primary barrier to comprehension for the control group, whereas the experimental group successfully overcame this barrier due to the pre-reading activity.

Discussion

The finding of this study demonstrates that pre-reading vocabulary activities incorporating visual support and contextual guessing can substantially enhance A2-B1 level learners' reading comprehension. The improved performance of the experimental group confirms that learners benefit from engaging with unfamiliar vocabulary before reading, especially when the activity encourages inferencing rather than memorization. This method stimulated students' analytical thinking, strengthened their lexical awareness, and provided a scaffold for deeper comprehension. The use of visual aids helped reduce cognitive load, allowing learners to focus more effectively on meaning construction during reading. This supports existing literature emphasizing the importance of pre-reading strategies in building reading confidence and comprehension skills. The result also highlights the limitations of traditional reading instruction, where students often struggle with unknown vocabulary during reading, leading to lower comprehension outcomes.

Conclusion

This exploratory action research demonstrates that a visual and contextual pre-reading vocabulary activity can significantly improve A2-B1 students' ability to identify the main ideas in short texts. The method promotes independent learning, contextual reasoning and deeper comprehension. Implementing similar strategies in regular language teaching may contribute to more effective reading instruction.

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